

**PERCEPTION OF POST-BASIC EDUCATION STUDENTS ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP
EDUCATION FOR SELF- RELIANCE IN BAUCHI METROPOLIS**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to find out the perception of post basic education students on entrepreneurial education for self-reliance in Bauchi metropolis. The study investigated the perception of students on entrepreneurship education. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study. The area of the study was Bauchi metropolis and the targeted population was all the students in post basic education (senior secondary school). The sample was drawn from 4 selected secondary schools, using simple random sampling technique, with a total of 200 respondents and the statistical tool for analysis was mean and standard deviation. Result showed that students are aware of entrepreneurship education and when properly guided, would choose viable careers of interest after graduation. Following these findings, recommendations are made and if implemented would help post basic education students to be self-employed.

Keywords: Students, Perception, Entrepreneurial, Education, Self-reliance

Introduction

Education is widely accepted as a leading instrument for promoting economic growth and development (Gómez & Valdés, 2019). In Africa, where growth and development are essential for poverty alleviation, education, particularly entrepreneurship education, becomes a critical factor for any meaningful development. It is therefore in the context of entrepreneurial development that the National Policy on Education (NPE 2013) calls for “functional education that would be relevant, practical, and allow for the acquisition of appropriate skills and development of competences as equipment for individuals to live in and contribute to the development of the society”. It opens the door for individuals to participate and contribute to economic development and self-sufficiency. The participation of the individual in creating wealth and contributing to economic development is a gate way to the individual’s economic security. Granic (2022) stated that “when people are denied educational opportunities, they are excluded from the development process”. The resultant effect of this exclusion is insecurity. Burchi (2013) submitted that security is an important aspect of the corporate existence, health and happiness of an individual or nation. To be secured, an individual or a nation should be economically free to follow, or choice of policies to develop his or her economy. In view of this, Light et al (2019) posited that: “The right to good education is the most obvious example, That is elevating a good education to the status of a right, that in any domains, education is indispensable

for decent prospects in life; that it is a basic safe guard of individual security; that those who are well-educated are less likely to fall, and, if they do, are more likely to pick themselves up; and education is necessary for citizenship itself". Therefore, economic security as defined by the International Labour Organization (ILO 2013) "is composed of basic security defined by access to basic needs, infrastructure pertaining to health, education, dwelling, information and social protection as well as work related security"., labour market security, employment security, job security, work security and skill reproduction security". It includes income representation security.

The national policy on education (FGN, 2013) rightly recognized the relevance of education to the development of an individual and the nation, hence endorsed that Nigeria's policy thrust for education should be geared towards using education as an instrument for achieving:

1. A free and democratic society
2. A just and egalitarian society
3. A united, strong and self-reliant nation
4. A great and dynamic economy
5. A land full of bright opportunities for all citizens (NPE, 2013)

Ternenge et al. (2020) maintained that, Entrepreneurship education is the type of education geared towards producing a self-employed or self-reliant person. It is directed towards instilling of such traits as innovativeness, ingenuity, resourcefulness and endurance. In entrepreneurship education, manipulation of effective human intelligence is developed for creative performance. In entrepreneurship education, the learner in the submission of Ogele, (2020) is taught how to become the centre of an integrated model of economic development who incorporates a theory of profit and interest, as well as the theory of the business cycle and the capitalist system. He becomes a pacesetter, an investor and a risk bearer who crafts energies. Entrepreneurship education enables its recipients to know how to gather resources, initiate action and establish an organization or enterprise to meet the demand of such organization or its market opportunity.

Statement of the Problem

Education is one of the basic fundamentals for economic development of the individual and society, while entrepreneurship education acts as the driver of its achievement, because of its emphasis on skill acquisition, attitudes and behaviours (Kuckertz, 2013). Unfortunately, the increasing number of unemployed has created economic, political, and security challenges in the society and high number of graduates from post basic education (senior secondary schools) could not gain admission to further their education keep compounding the problem of unemployment and joblessness among the youths of society. Many stakeholders have been agitating on the type of education received by the students since education has been established as an instrument for economic mobility and security. In view of the above, this study attempted to find out the Perception of Post-Basic Education Students on Entrepreneurship Education for Self- Reliance in Bauchi Metropolis.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the Perception of Post-Basic Education Students on Entrepreneurship Education for Self- Reliance in Bauchi metropolis. Specifically, the study aims at:

- i. Identifying the awareness of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis.
- ii. Examining the challenges faced by post basic education students in need of entrepreneurship in Bauchi metropolis.

- iii. Identifying the prospects of entrepreneurship among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of awareness of post basic students on entrepreneurial education in Bauchi metropolis.
- ii. What is the level of challenges faced by post basic education students in need of entrepreneurship in Bauchi metropolis.
- iii. What are the prospects of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis.

Research Design

The research design was a survey design, survey design is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only few people or items are studied considered to be representative of the entire group (Denscombe, 2017). The area of the study was Bauchi State. Bauchi State is one of the Thirty-Six (36) states of Nigeria located in the north-East geographical zone. The population for the study was all the students of post basic education (SSS 3) in Bauchi metropolis. The sample size of 200 students were drawn from the population using sample random sampling technique, 50 students were selected each from the 4 select schools, using replacement process. This process involved identifying all the students by number, starting from 1 to the last students in SS 3 as the case may be (Bhardwaj, 2019). These numbers were written each on a piece of paper rolled up, put in bag, shook up and picked. The first 50, one at a time with replacement until the sample size of 50 was obtained. This process was repeated in all the 4 selected schools which made the total sample size of 200 students. A structured questionnaire of 20 items was adapted from Uzoamaka, Ayolugbe and Igwe, (2019), and tagged “Perception of Post-Basic Education Students on Entrepreneurship Education for Self- Reliance in Bauchi Metropolis”. The questionnaire has 2 sections; section A consists of respondents’ personal data while section B, consists of 20 items that sought information on the awareness, prospects and challenges of entrepreneurship education for self-reliant. A structured questionnaire of 4 point rating scale, that is Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree as well as Highly Aware, Moderately Aware, Slightly aware and Not Aware, with the ratings of 4,3,2,1 respectively, and was developed by the researcher and validated by two experts in test and measurement from Department of Education Foundations of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Bauchi. Data Collection was through four trained research assistants in the selected schools, who administers the questionnaire and retrieve same from the respondents. The data was analyzed, using simple Mean and standard deviation to determine the level of awareness of post basic education students on entrepreneurship education in Bauchi Metropolis. The decision rule was that any mean of 2.5 and above was accepted while below was rejected.

Results and Discussion

Results

Research Question One: What is the level of awareness of post basic students on entrepreneurial education in Bauchi metropolis?

Table 1 (Perception of post basic students on entrepreneurship education for senior secondary school) reveals that students are aware of entrepreneurship offered in schools showing highest mean of 3.9. Others indicated in the table below according to order of perception include; entrepreneurship as the ability to perceive and undertake business opportunities (3.76), job preference after graduation (3.68), entrepreneurship as very important to the post basic education graduates of

senior secondary schools (3.66), entrepreneurship education as a form of education that seeks to provide knowledge, skills, attitude and motivation to students for success in any setting (3.64), awareness of entrepreneurship education (3.61), and plan to be self-employed in the near future (3.6).

Table 1: Level of awareness of post basic students on entrepreneurial education in Bauchi metropolis.

S/N	Item Description	Mean	SD	Decision
1	What is your level of awareness of entrepreneurship education	3.61	0.55	Accepted
2	Are you aware that this course is offered in your school	3.9	0.54	Accepted
3	Entrepreneurship education is a form of education that seeks to provide knowledge, skills, attitude and motivation to students for success in any setting.	3.64	0.71	Accepted
4	Entrepreneurship is very important to the post basic education graduates of senior secondary schools.	3.66	0.69	Accepted
5	Entrepreneurship is the ability to perceive And undertake business opportunities.	3.76	0.70	Accepted
6	Are you aware Guidance and counselling officer gives talk on Job preference after graduation	3.68	0.56	Accepted
7	Are you aware on how to Plan to be self-employed in the near future	3.6	0.73	Accepted

Source: Field survey, 2017.

From the table above it shows that the students are fully aware of entrepreneurship education and they all agree that entrepreneurship is the ability to perceive and undertake business opportunities. They also agree that the course is offered in their school and they have plans for self-employment.

Research Question Two: what is the level of challenges faced by post basic education students in need of entrepreneurship in Bauchi metropolis?

Table 2: Challenges faced by post basic education students in need of entrepreneurship in Bauchi metropolis

S/N	Items Description	Mean	SD	Decision
8	Entrepreneurship is a career option for graduates of post basic education	3.45	0.73	Accept
9	An entrepreneur needs proper guidance in selecting a vocation	3.83	0.72	Accept
10	If given training on entrepreneurship other than personal inclination, will you welcome it?	1.64	0.65	Rejected
11	A favourable attitude of the student toward entrepreneurial activities is both needed to motivate students to start a new business	3.63	0.55	Accept
12	Entrepreneurship is a tool for self-reliant	3.09	0.56	Accept
13	Entrepreneurship is a tool for job creation	3.75	0.77	Accept
14	Entrepreneurship creates wealth and financial independence	3.52	0.60	Accept

Source: Field survey, 2017.

The response obtained from the respondents on the challenges faced by post basic education students, on entrepreneurship education shows that entrepreneurship education is not well accepted by students of post basic education with a mean of 2.68. This may be due to the lack of awareness and not having capable hands or teachers that will tutor the student thoroughly on entrepreneurship education. Others indicated in the table below according to order of challenges include; In-availability of information on how to start a new business discourages students to become an entrepreneur (2.07), entrepreneurship education teaches risks and time management skills (1.93), Entrepreneurship education teaches problem solving skills (1.79), Entrepreneurship knowledge gives insight into financial management (1.63), Entrepreneurial skills involves creativity, innovations, development and perseverance (1.62)

Research Question Three: What are the prospects of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis?

Results on prospects of entrepreneurship on post basic education shows that an entrepreneur needs proper guidance in selecting a vocation (3.83), followed by entrepreneurship as a tool for job creation (3.75), by a favourable attitude of the student toward entrepreneurial activities is both needed to motivate students to start a new business (3.63), entrepreneurship is a career option for graduates of post basic education (3.45),if entrepreneurship training is given other than personal inclination (1.64), entrepreneurship creates wealth and financial independence (3.52), as a tool for self-reliant (3.09)

Table 3: Prospects of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Decision
15	Entrepreneurship education is not well accepted by students of post basic education	1.93	0.88	Rejected
16	There are enough teachers to teach Entrepreneurship education in my school	1.97	0.77	Rejected
17	Entrepreneurship education has many text books that guide us in my school	1.37	0.56	Rejected
18	Entrepreneurship education in my school has a demonstration resource centre	1.34	0.55	Rejected
19	My school encourage practical exercises on entrepreneurship to give knowledge and insight of what it means (Entrepreneurship)	3.54	0.82	Accepted
20	In-availability of information on how to start a new business discourages students to become an entrepreneur.	1.41	0.82	Rejected

Source:Fieldsurvey,2017.

Finding of the Study

1. The analysis research question one showed that, students are fully aware of entrepreneurship education and the courses it entails in their schools and that it provides knowledge, skills and attitudes and motivation to students. It is also agreed that it gives ability to perceive and undertake business opportunities also that it is done through guidance and counselling in the schools and all have plan for future self-employment
2. The analysis research question two showed that despite the responses on research question one and believe in the available prospect in entrepreneurship education, there are challenges that faces it, including lack of enough and qualified teachers, text books in-availability of information on how to start a business and this lead to non-acceptability of the course by post basic education.

3. The analysis on research question three showed that, all the students agreed that entrepreneurship has prospect as a career option for graduates of post basic education students when there is a proper guidance in the selection of vocation, given the right training in the direction of personal inclination with students' favourable attitude toward entrepreneurship activities and entrepreneurship tools for self-reliance and ability for job creation as well as wealth and financial independence

Discussion of the Findings

From the analysis of research question one which identified the awareness of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students, indicated that students are fully aware of entrepreneurship education in their schools and it is offered as a subject and benefits accrued to a career in entrepreneurship this agrees with Ahmed, Chandran and Klobas (2017).

Analysis of research question two which sought to find out the level of challenges faced by post basic education students in need of entrepreneurship, showed that if the required resources for entrepreneurship education are put in place, it would enable students to make good career choices in it, as postulated by Iro-Idoro et al. (2015). National transformation agenda as a veritable tool for challenges facing entrepreneurship education in federal polytechnics in Nigeria:

The analysis of research question three, which examined the prospects of entrepreneurship education among post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis, it was discovered that the students perceive entrepreneurship as a means of poverty alleviation, self-reliant and economic independence as a prospect of entrepreneurship education as identified by Akpochafo, and Alika (2018). Perceived Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Career Development among Undergraduates in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study was to find out the perception of students of post basic education on entrepreneurship education for self-reliance in Bauchi metropolis. The study was guided by three objectives which include identifying the perception of students, prospect of entrepreneurship education and what are the challenges faced by students of post basic education. Three research questions were formulated thus; what is the perception of post basic education on entrepreneurship education; what are the prospects of entrepreneurship education on post basic education students and what are the challenges faced by students of post basic education on entrepreneurship education.

The outcome of this study is expected to benefit the students by utilizing the rear opportunity available to them on entrepreneurial education in their schools, making use of guidance and counselling services on entrepreneurship education, as well as critically analyzing the prospects identified to see where they fit best, furthermore it will help them to learn skills and competences in vocations of their inclination and be self-employed after graduation as well as become economic independent. The study was delimited to post basic education students in Bauchi metropolis of Plateau State.

Based on the result of this study, it was concluded that since the students are aware of entrepreneurship education, it could be used to be creators of wealth rather than become job seekers after graduation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were hereby proffered: -

Since students are aware of entrepreneurship education more all required resources should be put in place for the realization of the objectives of entrepreneurship education. Furthermore all the foreseen challenges in all aspects of entrepreneurship education be resolved to allow full participation of all the students.

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